

Testing Usability of Sentinel-2 Seasonal Variations for Non-Forest Plant Cover Mapping – Small-Scale Study in NW Croatia

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Abstract: Areas occupied by grasslands, arable land and natural succession are continuously changing over time. Due to these dynamics, reliable and comprehensive data on their distribution in Croatia remain only partially available. Remote sensing may offer an effective solution for large-scale identification and monitoring of non-forest plant cover, including the spread of grassland succession on abandoned grasslands. The aim of this study is to assess the potential of combining Sentinel-2 imagery with Discriminant Analysis (DA) and Classification Trees (CT) to differentiate categories of non-forest plant cover. Research was conducted on the south-eastern slopes of Medvednica Mt., within the wider Goranec Protected landscape. 59 polygons of interest were classified as grasslands, grassland successions, and annual crops. Centroids of a 10 m grid were used for sampling four spectral bands (blue, green, red, NIR) acquired between March and October 2024. Descriptive statistics highlighted distinct seasonal trends in May, July, and October in the spectral bands, which were selected as predictor variables. Overall, the CT model had higher accuracy (82%) than DA model (70%), but when compared at the category level, DA had higher accuracy for succession (86%), while CT for grasslands (90%) and arable land (48%). Consensus on accurately classified cases between the models was lowest for arable land (31%) and highest for grasslands (70%), with DA showing a tendency to overestimate succession, while CT overestimates grasslands. Initial results confirm the potential of Sentinel-2 data for classification of non-forest plant cover providing a cost-efficient tool for land monitoring and conservation planning, although additional testing and model tuning are needed.

Keywords: spectral signatures; grasslands; succession; land use.

1 Introduction

Rural land abandonment has become a prominent component of global change in Europe, particularly in mountainous regions, where large areas of agricultural land are being progressively abandoned (Perpiña Castillo et al. 2018). These processes lead to complex ecological outcomes, including shifts in plant communities from early colonizing to late-successional stages, accompanied by changes in soil properties and ecosystem functioning (Molina et al. 2023). While abandonment can temporarily enhance biodiversity and ecosystem services, it alters traditional landscapes and habitat availability (Valverde-Asenjo et al. 2020). Semi-natural grasslands are among the most endangered terrestrial ecosystems in Europe, whose distribution and conservation status strongly depend on

land-use history and management practices, as the cessation of grazing and mowing often leads to shrub encroachment and forest succession (Cvitanović et al. 2017, Habel et al. 2013). These changes are particularly pronounced in mountain areas, where land abandonment has been widely documented as a major driver of vegetation dynamics (Kolecka et al. 2015). Monitoring such dynamic and heterogeneous processes remains challenging. Vegetation changes during succession are often subtle and difficult to distinguish using conventional methods, particularly at larger spatial scales (Kolecka et al. 2015). In this context, remote sensing has become an essential tool for land cover mapping due to its increasing spatial and temporal resolution and data availability (DeFries 2013). Multispectral imagery from Sentinel-2 enables detailed analysis of vegetation patterns, although the discrimination of spectrally similar classes remains problematic (Rossi et al. 2025, Jogun et al. 2019). Therefore, this study aims to assess the potential of combining Sentinel-2 imagery with Discriminant Analysis and Classification Trees to differentiate non-forest vegetation. This could lead to improved cost-effective land monitoring and conservation planning.

2 Materials and methods

The research was conducted on the south-eastern slopes of Medvednica Mt., within the wider Goranec protected landscape in Croatia. The study area is, besides forest, characterized by a heterogeneous mosaic of grasslands, agricultural land, and areas undergoing natural succession, reflecting ongoing land-use changes.

2.1 Field data collection and classification

Polygons of interest were defined based on field surveys conducted in 2024–2025 and supplemented with publicly available spatial data. A total of 59 polygons were classified into three categories: 26 grasslands, 15 grassland successions, and 18 annual crops, representing dominant types of non-forest vegetation cover in the study area (Figure 1).

2.2 Remote sensing data and sampling

Sentinel-2 multispectral satellite imagery was used for analysis. Spectral data were acquired between March and October 2024 to capture seasonal variability in vegetation. Because of Sentinel's spatial resolution of 10 m, a grid of the same size was generated, and its centroid points were used as sampling locations. For each centroid, values of four spectral bands—blue, green, red, and near-infrared (IR)—were extracted. Descriptive statistical analysis was

Figure 5. Locations of 59 sampling polygons (grassland, succession, annual crops) overlaid on Sentinel-2 10 m grid.

Figure 6. Distinctive values for green band in May, July and October. Box: mean, Whisker: Non-Outlier Range.

applied to identify seasonal patterns in spectral responses, with May, July, and October showing the most distinct differences among classes. Variables from these months were therefore selected as predictors for classification.

2.3 Classification methods

Two classification approaches were applied: Discriminant Analysis (DA) with forward selection and Classification Trees (CT). DA was used as a parametric statistical method to model the separation between three predefined classes based on linear combinations of predictor variables. The number of classification functions corresponds to the number of the existing groups. In parallel, CT were employed as a non-parametric method that produce a series of nested “if-then-else” splits for separation of cases into groups. A CART-style exhaustive search for univariate splits was used as a split selection method with Gini measure of goodness of fit and FACT-style direct stopping was used as a stopping rule (i.e. selection of the right-sized tree) in the process of building a binary decision tree in STATISTICA 14.0.0.15 TIBCO Software Inc.

Both models were trained using the selected spectral variables and evaluated in terms of overall classification accuracy and class-level performance, allowing for comparison of their effectiveness in distinguishing between grasslands, succession areas and arable land.

3 Results

Descriptive statistics of the spectral bands show distinct seasonal trends in May, July, and October. Blue, green, and red bands differentiate annual crops with higher mean values from grasslands and grassland successions in May (blue-1628 vs 1424/1367; green-2004 vs 1753/1681; red-1974 vs 1546/1466) and October (blue-1510 vs 1376/1345; green-1797 vs 1642/1586; red-1754 vs 1507/1500). Blue and green bands differentiate grassland successions, with lower mean values from grasslands/annual crops in July (blue-1375 vs 1492/1463; green-1642 vs 1777/1738) (Figure 2).

The CT model (Figure 3) demonstrates a hierarchical decision structure. The distribution of cases within nodes indicates that grasslands dominate the dataset, which is also reflected in the classification outcomes. Accuracy assessment of the CT model (Table 1) shows improved performance compared to DA for certain classes. Grasslands were classified with the highest accuracy (90%), followed by succession (68%) and arable land (48%).

Classification functions derived from DA are:

$$\text{Suc: } -350.963 + 0.188 \cdot \text{MayGREEN} - 0.123 \cdot \text{MayRED} - 0.007 \cdot \text{MayIR} + 0.498 \cdot \text{JulBLUE} - 0.097 \cdot \text{JulGREEN} - 0.141 \cdot \text{JulRED} + 0.037 \cdot \text{JulIR} + 0.275 \cdot \text{OctBLUE} - 0.104 \cdot \text{OctGREEN} - 0.067 \cdot \text{OctRED}$$

$$\text{Gra: } -359.638 + 0.191 \cdot \text{MayGREEN} - 0.122 \cdot \text{MayRED} - 0.007 \cdot \text{MayIR} + 0.488 \cdot \text{JulBLUE} - 0.094 \cdot \text{JulGREEN} - 0.134 \cdot \text{JulRED} + 0.036 \cdot \text{JulIR} + 0.283 \cdot \text{OctBLUE} - 0.103 \cdot \text{OctGREEN} - 0.072 \cdot \text{OctRED}$$

$$\text{Ara: } -377.461 + 0.185 \cdot \text{MayGREEN} - 0.110 \cdot \text{MayRED} - 0.006 \cdot \text{MayIR} + 0.479 \cdot \text{JulBLUE} - 0.113 \cdot \text{JulGREEN} - 0.122 \cdot \text{JulRED} + 0.038 \cdot \text{JulIR} + 0.281 \cdot \text{OctBLUE} - 0.092 \cdot \text{OctGREEN} - 0.072 \cdot \text{OctRED}$$

Figure 7. CT model for three classes of land cover developed with Sentinel 10m spectral bands from May, July and October. Numbers above nodes (rectangles) indicate number of cases sent to that node. Number in the upper left part of the node is a node number, while labels in the upper right corner denote the predicted class. In each node histograms indicate proportions of cases in each class at node. Terminal nodes are drawn with a red line, and decision (split) nodes with blue one.

Table 2. Accuracy matrix for DA and CT. Rows represent observed classes, columns represent predicted classes. Overall accuracy is given in the last row, while class-specific accuracies are shown for each land cover type.

observed		DA				CT			
		suc	gra	ara	%accuracy	suc	gra	ara	%accuracy
419	suc	361	58	0	0.86	285	130	4	0.68
1979	gra	539	1436	4	0.73	149	1789	41	0.90
314	ara	51	167	96	0.31	18	145	151	0.48
2712	predicted	951	1661	100	0.70	452	2064	196	0.82

Table 3. Comparison of DA and CT model predictions. Values represent the number of samples assigned to each class. Background colours indicate observed classes: orange – succession; green – grasslands; grey – arable land (e.g. 16 cases of arable land cover were classified as succession both by the CT and DA model). Values in bold highlight agreement between models on observed classes.

		CT predicted								
		suc	gra	ara	suc	gra	ara	suc	gra	ara
DA predicted	suc	264	96	1	124	413	2	16	34	1
	gra	21	34	3	25	1376	35	2	111	54
	ara	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	96

They indicate that spectral bands from all three acquisition periods contributed to class separation. MayBLUE and OctIR were omitted from the final models. Accuracy assessment of the DA model (Table 1) shows uneven performance overall across classes. The highest classification accuracy was achieved for succession (86%), followed by grasslands (73%), with arable land having substantially lower accuracy (31%). Misclassification was particularly pronounced between grasslands and succession, and grasslands and arable land, indicating spectral overlap among these classes.

A comparison of predictions from both models (Table 2) reveals cases of agreement and divergence in classification patterns. A substantial number of cases were consistently classified as grasslands by both models, reflecting the

robustness of this class. However, discrepancies are evident for succession and arable land, where misclassifications frequently occurred between these categories and grasslands. Grasslands were often over-predicted, particularly in the CT model, which aligns with its higher classification accuracy for this class.

4 Discussion

The results demonstrate that Sentinel-2 multispectral data can be effectively used to differentiate non-forest vegetation classes, although classification performance varies depending on both the method applied and the spectral similarity among classes. Both DA and CT successfully identified general patterns in land cover, confirming previous findings that medium-resolution

satellite imagery is suitable for large-scale vegetation mapping and monitoring (Pelletier et al. 2019).

Higher accuracy of the CT model for grasslands (90%) compared to DA (73%) is consistent with studies showing that tree-based methods are particularly effective in handling non-linear relationships and complex class boundaries in remote sensing data (Belgiu and Drăguț 2016). Grasslands likely exhibit more consistent spectral signatures across seasons, which facilitates their classification, especially when multi-temporal data are used. In contrast, the relatively lower performance of both models for arable land, particularly in DA (31%), can be attributed to high temporal variability caused by agricultural practices such as ploughing, harvesting, and crop rotation. Additional aggravating factors could be crop type variability and growth stage (Simeón et al. 2025). Similar challenges in distinguishing arable land from other vegetation types have been reported (Pelletier et al. 2019).

The confusion between succession areas and grasslands observed in both models reflects their ecological and spectral similarity, especially in early successional stages. This finding aligns with previous research indicating that transitional vegetation types are difficult to separate using optical remote sensing alone, due to overlapping spectral responses (Lu et al. 2004). Although DA performed better in identifying succession (86%), misclassification patterns suggest that it may not fully capture the complexity of vegetation gradients. The importance of seasonal data supports the use of multi-temporal approaches for improving separability and classification accuracy (Simeón et al. 2025). Phenological differences between vegetation types enhance separability, a conclusion widely supported in the literature (Griffiths et al. 2013).

5 Conclusions

Sentinel-2 imagery combined with Discriminant Analysis and Classification Trees proved effective for classifying non-forest vegetation types. Model performance varied by class, with DA better identifying succession and CT performing best for grasslands. Both models exhibited limitations, particularly in distinguishing spectrally similar classes, leading to misclassification. Our findings highlight the importance of method selection and the challenges associated with mapping heterogeneous and transitional vegetation types. Future research should incorporate additional data (e.g. high-resolution imagery and vegetation indices) and advanced methods (e.g. machine learning) to further improve classification accuracy and support more reliable monitoring of land cover dynamics.

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